

Exertional Rhabdomyolysis in Athletes: A Review of Pathophysiology, Diagnosis and Treatment

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Abstract

Objective:

In recent years popularity of endurance training and high-intensity sports has grown. While physical activity remains a crucial part of a healthy lifestyle, inadequate preparation or overexertion may lead to developing exertional rhabdomyolysis (ER), a potentially fatal condition. This narrative review aims to synthesise current evidence on pathophysiology, risk factors, clinical and laboratory findings, and treatment of exertional rhabdomyolysis in both professional and amateur athletes.

Methods:

A narrative review of the literature was conducted using published meta-analyses, systematic and clinical reviews addressing risk factors, epidemiology, diagnostic and therapeutic recommendations in patients with ER with additional focus on the mechanism of development of acute kidney injury (AKI) and its treatment.

Results:

Information contained in the reviewed literature was successfully synthesised into an article containing information on pathophysiology of ER itself, as well as of AKI caused by ER, factors increasing the likelihood of developing ER, as well as presentation of symptoms, laboratory findings, methods of treatment, and on how to safely return to physical activity after an episode of ER.

Conclusions:

Exertional rhabdomyolysis is one of the most serious complications of excessively strenuous exercise. Proper hydration and avoiding overexertion play an important role in reducing the risk of developing ER (4, 9, 12). Identification of symptoms and proper assessment of laboratory findings, especially serum creatine kinase (CK) levels, is crucial in making the proper diagnosis (3). Quick administration of intravenous rehydration therapy is the most important intervention in patients with ER (4,7). Renal replacement therapy plays an important role in treating patients who developed AKI (6, 10, 17). After successful treatment, a gradual return to sport is possible if there are no indications of possible recurrence of ER (4, 8).

Keywords: Exertional rhabdomyolysis; acute kidney injury; dehydration; high-intensity exercise; myoglobinuria

Introduction

The growing popularity of high-intensity training programmes, endurance sports, and recreational fitness activities has led to an increasing number of reports of exertional rhabdomyolysis (ER) among both professional athletes and amateurs (4). While regular physical activity is widely recognised as a necessary part of a healthy lifestyle and often advised by health professionals, excessive or unaccustomed exertion may result in significant muscle injury with potentially serious consequences, including acute kidney injury (AKI) or life-threatening arrhythmias. Exertional rhabdomyolysis is a clinical condition characterised by the breakdown of muscle fibres and the release of intracellular contents, including myoglobin, creatine kinase, electrolytes, and other muscle proteins, into the circulation.

Despite the rising incidence of exertional rhabdomyolysis, awareness among athletes, trainers, and even healthcare professionals remains limited. Early recognition and appropriate management are crucial in preventing serious complications and ensuring a safe return to physical activity. This article aims to review the current understanding of exertional rhabdomyolysis, with particular emphasis on its pathophysiology, risk factors, clinical presentation, laboratory findings, management, and outcomes.

Pathophysiology

Rhabdomyolysis is a clinical syndrome resulting from the breakdown of skeletal muscle fibres and the subsequent release of muscle proteins and electrolytes into the systemic circulation. In exertional rhabdomyolysis, muscle injury is primarily caused by depletion of intracellular adenosine triphosphate (ATP) (9, 15, 17). ATP depletion leads to dysfunction of the Na⁺/Ca²⁺ ATPase, which in turn leads to dysfunction of the Na⁺/K⁺ ATPase pump (5, 9, 16, 18). The effect is the accumulation of calcium ions inside muscle cells.

Elevated intracellular calcium activates calcium-dependent proteases, phospholipases, and endonucleases, which contribute to the degradation of structural proteins and ultimately muscle cell necrosis (14, 16, 18). As a consequence, large amounts of muscle-derived proteins and electrolytes, including myoglobin, creatine kinase, potassium, and phosphate, are released into the bloodstream. In addition to exertional causes, rhabdomyolysis may also result from infections, medications, crush injuries, electrolyte disturbances, drug or toxin exposure, as well as states of hypothermia or hyperthermia (5, 9, 11, 14, 18).

Acute kidney injury (AKI) is one of the most severe complications of rhabdomyolysis. It occurs in about 20-60% of patients presenting with rhabdomyolysis (6) and arises through three interrelated pathophysiological mechanisms (6, 9). Renal vasoconstriction occurs as a result of intravascular volume depletion caused by sequestration of extracellular fluid into damaged muscle tissue. This reduction in effective circulating volume leads to decreased renal perfusion and activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system, which causes constriction of afferent arterioles, thus further exacerbating renal ischemia (9, 10, 17).

Tubular obstruction is another mechanism of kidney damage. Excessive glomerular filtration of myoglobin leads to its binding with Tamm-Horsfall protein within the distal tubules, resulting in the formation of obstructive casts that decrease tubular flow (5, 9, 17). Moreover, a portion of filtered myoglobin is reabsorbed by proximal tubular cells, where it undergoes lysosomal degradation. This process releases free iron, which accumulates intracellularly and promotes oxidative stress by creating free radicals (9, 10). The resulting lipid peroxidation and cellular injury further contribute to tubular dysfunction.

Together, renal vasoconstriction, tubular obstruction, and the direct cytotoxic effects of myoglobin and iron-mediated oxidative injury lead to the development of acute kidney injury in patients with rhabdomyolysis.

Risk factors

There are several risk factors associated with an increased likelihood of developing exertional rhabdomyolysis (ER). Athletes who suddenly intensify their exercise regimen are particularly vulnerable. Similarly, individuals who have only recently initiated a structured exercise program, especially those with low baseline fitness levels, are at elevated risk due to a higher risk of muscle injury (4, 11). Inadequate recovery between training sessions further contributes to cumulative muscle damage.

Certain types of physical activity have been shown to carry a higher risk of inducing rhabdomyolysis, such as exercises involving eccentric muscle contractions. During eccentric contractions, muscles generate force while simultaneously lengthening, which results in greater mechanical stress on muscle fibres and causes damage to their protein structure (7, 11, 12, 15). This includes activities such as downhill running or lowering of weights during biceps curls. Long-distance running has also been associated with a higher risk of developing ER, further complicated by AKI (12).

Dehydration constitutes another major risk factor, particularly in relation to the development of kidney injury. Insufficient fluid intake, excessive sweating, or training in hot and humid environments can lead to hypovolemia and reduced renal perfusion (4, 9, 12, 13). This not only exacerbates muscle ischemia and injury but also impairs the kidneys' ability to clear myoglobin and other nephrotoxic products released during muscle breakdown. Moreover, electrolytic imbalances that may be present in hypovolemia, such as hyper- or hyponatraemia, may further exacerbate muscle injury (5, 10, 12). As a result, dehydration significantly increases the risk of acute kidney injury in individuals with exertional rhabdomyolysis.

Pharmacological factors also play an important role in predisposing individuals to ER. Several commonly prescribed medications, including statins, antihistamines, antipsychotics, and selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs), have been associated with an increased risk of muscle injury (9, 16, 17, 18). Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are of particular concern due to their potential nephrotoxicity and widespread use among athletes for pain management (4, 9, 11, 13).

Additional contributing factors include recent infections, as well as alcohol consumption, which can impair muscle regeneration and promote dehydration (4, 5, 9, 17, 18). The coexistence of multiple risk factors substantially increases the likelihood of developing exertional rhabdomyolysis and underscores the importance of early recognition and preventive strategies in athletic populations.

The role of creatine, a popular supplement among many athletes, in inducing ER remains debated. However, most data indicate that consumption of standard amounts of creatine is not a risk factor for developing ER (11). Some research even shows a protective effect of creatine on muscle injury and inflammation (1,2). No link has also been found between creatine consumption and increased risk of kidney injury (11). Thus, it can be argued that creatine plays no role in causing or exacerbating exertional rhabdomyolysis and may even have some protective effect.

Diagnosis

Symptoms in patients with exertional rhabdomyolysis may range from mild or even asymptomatic to life-threatening. The classic triad of symptoms includes myalgia, weakness, and myoglobinuria, a pathognomonic symptom of rhabdomyolysis, which usually presents as dark or tea-coloured urine (4, 5, 9, 16). However, the presence of all three symptoms has been observed in less than 10% of patients (16, 18). Other symptoms include oedema, fever, nausea, confusion, agitation, and anuria (5, 10, 17, 18). In severe cases, it can lead to hyperkalaemia, disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC), and cardiac arrhythmias (4, 5, 10, 18). Up to 50% of patients may be asymptomatic (9).

The most characteristic and sensitive laboratory marker is an elevated serum creatine kinase (CK) level, which reflects skeletal muscle injury (3). CK levels typically rise within 2-12 hours after muscle injury, peak

within 24-72 hours, and gradually decline over several days at a rate of about 40% a day (9, 12). Mild-to-moderate elevation of CK is routinely present in athletes after exercise and bears no clinical significance (9). Levels exceeding 5-10 times the upper limit of normal are commonly used for diagnosis (12), while values above 5,000 U/L are reportedly associated with an increased risk of acute kidney injury (14).

The presence of myoglobinuria may be proven by using a urine dipstick, which will typically be positive for blood in urine. Upon further microscopic examination of the sample, no erythrocytes should be detected, indicating the presence of myoglobin (4, 10, 15, 16). Urine sediment analysis will show the presence of myoglobin casts and dead epithelial cells (9, 10). Moreover, transient glucosuria may be present in urinalysis (9). Urine testing may be positive in as low as 19% of cases; thus, the absence of urine myoglobin is insufficient in ruling out rhabdomyolysis (10).

Myoglobin serum levels may also be measured. However, due to its short plasma half-life of 1 to 3-6 hours (5, 10), the diagnosis of rhabdomyolysis cannot be ruled out based on the lack of serum myoglobin (4, 5, 10).

Monitoring creatinine and blood urea nitrogen (BUN) is important in assessing kidney function (5, 9, 10). Creatinine levels may be disproportionately elevated due to increased release of creatine caused by muscle breakdown and not correspond with actual renal performance (3, 9, 17). An elevated BUN/creatinine ratio may indicate dehydration (10).

Electrolyte imbalances caused by the release of high levels of calcium and potassium into the circulation are common. Hyperkalaemia is the most clinically significant due to the risk of it causing life-threatening arrhythmias and cardiac arrest (5, 9, 15). Hyperphosphatemia, hypocalcaemia, and hypercalcaemia may also be present (5, 9, 10). Monitoring electrolytic imbalances through electrolyte levels and ECG plays an important role in detecting potentially life-threatening arrhythmias (5, 17, 18).

Metabolic acidosis may be present, caused by the release of lactic acid and phosphate into the circulation and further exacerbated by impaired renal function (5, 9, 10, 16).

Coagulation studies, such as coagulation panel, D-dimer, and fibrinogen levels, should be considered to rule out the risk of DIC (4, 10).

Treatment

In patients with exertional rhabdomyolysis, treatment should be guided by both clinical presentation of symptoms and laboratory findings. Therapeutic strategy usually focuses on three objectives: stopping further muscle damage, preventing or minimising the effects of acute kidney injury (AKI), and preventing other serious, potentially life-threatening complications such as arrhythmias (10).

Intensive intravenous hydration plays an important role in minimising kidney damage in patients with ER (4, 7). Isotonic 0.9% sodium chloride is usually the preferred IV fluid, though other compounds may be necessary depending on laboratory findings (7). In hyperkalaemia, for example, sodium bicarbonate should be added to the IV fluid (10). The rate of intravenous rehydration should also depend on laboratory findings. The desired therapeutic effect is obtaining a urine output of about 200-300ml/h (4, 9, 14, 16, 18). This may require an initial administration of as much as 1-2 litres of fluid per hour until receiving a stable urine output (4, 15, 17). Comorbidities such as heart failure should also be factored in when deciding upon the rehydration rate (4, 18).

Alkalinisation of urine using bicarbonate is also a common intervention. This method of treatment stems from a theory that since the precipitation and formation of myoglobin casts in renal tubules occur in an acidic environment, alkalinisation should thus decrease the intensity of cast formation. However, there is a lack of substantial evidence confirming the efficacy of this therapeutic strategy. (9, 10, 14, 17)

Renal replacement therapy should be considered if AKI progresses despite intensive fluid administration. Indications for hemodialysis include metabolic acidosis, hyperkalemia, azotemia, and volume overload (6, 10, 17). Continuous renal replacement therapy (CRRT) is the most effective method of removing myoglobin from the system (6).

Treatment of hypocalcemia is not routinely recommended due to the high concentration of calcium in muscle cells, which may be prone to precipitation in the circulation, leading to either normocalcaemia or hypercalcaemia (8, 10, 17). Hypocalcaemia should be treated however in case of symptomatic hypocalcaemia (tetany), as well as hypocalcaemia copresent with hyperkalaemia and ECG changes (10, 17).

Prognosis and return to sport

Outcomes in exertional rhabdomyolysis vary considerably depending on the severity of muscle injury, timeliness of treatment, and the presence of comorbidities. Reported mortality rates in rhabdomyolysis range from 7% to 20% (9). Patients who develop acute kidney injury have consistently been shown to have higher mortality, with rates approaching 50% among those requiring renal replacement therapy (8). Hyperkalaemia constitutes an additional mortality risk factor due to the increased likelihood of life-threatening cardiac arrhythmias and cardiac arrest (9, 16, 18).

There are no definitive guidelines on when patients can return to physical activity. Risk of recurrence of exertional rhabdomyolysis should be assessed (4, 9). Factors associated with a higher risk of recurrence include: renal injury, developing ER after low-to-moderate physical activity, peak CK levels above 100,000 IU/L, CK elevation for more than 2 weeks despite rest, and previous history of ER (4). All patients should refrain from exercise until their CK levels return to normal or at least below five times the upper norm. Repeat CK level measurements should be performed every 72 hours. When CK levels normalise, patients may begin light activities, combined with a follow-up visit in about a week (8). If no symptoms are present, patients should gradually return to previous levels of physical activity (4, 8). Exercising in hot environment and performing exercises with eccentric contractions should be avoided during the recovery period (4). Adequate hydration during exercise is advised in order to reduce the risk of recurrence (4).

Conclusions

Both professional and amateur athletes are at risk of developing exertional rhabdomyolysis if exercising incorrectly (11). Proper hydration and avoiding overexertion play a crucial role in mitigating the risk of muscle injury (4, 11). Clinical picture may vary between individuals, common symptoms include muscle pain and swelling, fatigue and dark coloured urine, though they rarely all present together in a patient (16, 18). Monitoring CK levels is important in diagnosing rhabdomyolysis, as well as determining the efficacy of treatment (3). Other important laboratory tests include urinalysis and monitoring serum electrolyte levels (4, 9, 10). Intensive rehydration therapy plays a vital role in minimising the negative impact of rhabdomyolysis on kidney function (4, 7). When AKI progresses despite intravenous hydration, renal replacement therapy should be considered (6, 10, 17). After successful treatment, the likelihood of the recurrence of ER should be assessed (4, 8). In case of low possibility of another ER episode, patients may gradually return to previous levels of physical activity (4, 8).

Disclosure

Author Contributions:

- **Conceptualisation:** [MS], [PR]
- **Methodology:** [MS], [AB], [AP]
- **Software:** [MS], [AB]
- **Check:** [MS], [PR]
- **Formal analysis:** [MS], [AP]
- **Data curation:** [PR], [AB],
- **Writing-rough preparation:** [PR], [AB], [AP], [MS],
- **Writing-review and editing:** [MS], [AP]
- **Supervision:** [PR], [AB]

Conflict of interest: The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Funding Statement: Not applicable.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The authors confirm that the data supporting this study are available in the article's references.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

All authors have read and agreed with the published version of the manuscript

Declaration on the use of AI: In preparing this work, the authors used Grammarly in order to improve language and readability, text formatting, and verification of bibliographic styles. After using this tool/service, the authors have reviewed and edited the content as needed and accept full responsibility for the substantive content of the publication.

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